

16 Bit Microprocessor Architecture Analysis using VHDL

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Abstract:- This paper involves the design and simulation of 16 bit microprocessor architecture on FPGA using VHDL. Significant features such as the , increased speed ,minimal implementation real-estate, reduction in power and maximum configurability are provided by several FPGAs. Where earlier a design may have included 6 to 10 ASICs, but today the same design can be achieved using only single FPGA.VHDL is used in order to programme FPGA.VHDL is very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language. This model actually represents the textual description of a hardware design or a piece of design which, when simulated mimics the design behaviour .The processor contains a number of basic modules. These modules are register array of 8X16 bit register, an ALU, shift register, program counter , an instruction register ,an address register, a comparator and control unit. All of these units or modules are assembled together and communicate through a common 16 bit tristate data bus.

Keywords:- Register transfer level, Reduced instruction set computer(RISC), Very high speed integrated circuit(VHSIC) hardware description language , Arithmetic logic unit(ALU), Field programmable gate array(FPGA).

I. INTRODUCTION

The requirements for the language were being first generated in 1980s, under the title Very High Speed Integrated Circuit (VHSIC) project of US government, in order to enhance the electronic technology, design process, and procurement, as well as the development of many advanced IC process technologies. Any hardware design can be described in terms of its operations at

different levels of abstraction, from system through to logic gates. At each level of this hierarchy the overall inputs and outputs remain the same but the functionality of distinct sections become clearer with the help of detailed schematics.

IC design indulges in more complex computations as compare with the software version and found to be time consuming .The design needed to develop such as microprocessor of required specification by conventional approach will lead to reduction in machine cycle, variation in data bus size, reduction in cost, and implementation of all numbering system. After implementing such a system, major questions raises in the shape of its integration and optimization. These problems have been eliminated by Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) technology and by Hardware Descriptive Language(HDL).The software interface along with chip design and planner reduces the complexity and enhances the ease of computations .[5],[6],[7].

With the proposed design in this paper, the 64 KB memory is interfaced with the CPU and the minimised delay, clock period, path delay are obtained. The proposed design has been tested with some application programs of memory- related operations (load, store, move, and branch).

II. TECHNICAL WORK PREPARATION

Various tools are put forth in designing of this system. In the present case microprocessor is bricked up using synthesized operations in the form of objectives and broader aspects. Fig. 1.shows the organization of the paper design that is needed to implement:

Fig 1. Composition of paper design with aims and objectives.

A. System overview

The main focus amongst them for Operational Design , Software Design and Hardware Design.

B. Operational overview

The operational view deals with various kinds of operation which a microprocessor can perform. The CPU (Central Processing Unit) is the “brain” of computer. It is composed of several parts , like data path, control path and memory units. At each clock cycle, Control Unit is needed to generate the control signals automatically for operating the data path. It is based on the finite state machine concept. The control unit for a processor basically cycles through three main steps, usually referred to as the instruction cycle i.e Fetch an instruction, Decodes the instruction and Executes the instruction. Second part deals with the Arithmetic Logic Unit which perform arithmetic computations such as addition ,subtraction, multiplication, division, increment, decrement and logical functions such as AND ,OR , XOR ,left shift ,right shift etc [7].

C. Software overview

Interfacing with VHDL software used in this system, reduces the complexity and also provide the graphic presentation of the system.VHDL is advantageous when used for systems design is that it allows the behavior of the required system to be described(modeled) and verified (simulated) before synthesis tools translate the design into real hardware (gates and wires).This not only indulge in compilation but also produces waveform results. For performing compilation and simulation of any logic circuit design, few sophisticated Computer Aided Design(CAD) tools such as Alteras II and Xilinx web pack are used [10].

D. Hardware overview

The Fundamental building block of microprocessor is shown in fig 2. This model instantiates components **CPU** and **memory** and specifies the necessary signals to connect the components, as shown in figure below.

Fig. 2: Hardware representation of 16 bit microprocessor

Component **mem** is a memory device and contains the instructions and data for the CPU to execute. Component **cpu** is an RTL implementation of the CPU device that is simulated for correctness and synthesized to implement the design. It includes clock signal ,reset valid memory address(VMA),address register,ready signal and data is required for operation.A final point is that when a VHDL model [11] is translated into the "gates and wires" that are mapped onto a programmable logic device such as a CPLD or FPGA, and then it is the actual hardware being configured, rather than the VHDL code being "executed" as if on some form of a processor chip.

Instruction register is for storing the instruction being fetched from the memory. The program counter holds the address of the memory of the current instruction. After the execution of instruction, the program counter move to the next instruction. If there is branch instruction, the program counter is loaded with the address of the next instruction . Then the value of the program counter is copied by the control unit to the address register, which gives the new address in address bus .The process of storing data into memory is called writing and retrieving data or opcode from the memory is called reading.

III. RESULTS

Synthesis and simulation of the VHDL code of the processor using Xilinx Software (Version 9.1) is presented. The synthesis and simulation results are presented for justification .Using Xilinx ISE 9.1 software the code is tested and checked. The simulation results are compared with the theoretical results. Before the start of simulation, the instructions and data are written and loaded into the memory. The processor with memory is tested for arithmetic and logical operations . When the VHDL code is fully synthesized, then the code is loaded to the Spartan FPGA device[8].

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS OF MICROPROCESSOR

Fig. 3: reset state

This state executes according to the state machine modelling as the sequential process sets signal **current_state** to state value **reset1**. This is the first state of the reset sequence for the CPU which starts the process of getting the CPU ready to execute instructions. the CPU ready to execute instructions .If the reset signal is not ‘1’ and there is a rising edge on the clock signal, then the **next state** signal generated by the combinational process is copied to signal **current_state**. This is the method for the state machine to advance from one state to another. After the **reset** signal is set to a value other than

‘1’, the state machine is in state **reset1**. Moving further control passes to state reset 2,reset3,reset 4,reset 5 and finally goes to reset 6 and, depending on the value of the ready signal from the memory, either stays in **reset6** or writes the memory data value to register **InstrReg** and goes to state **execute**. At this point, the state machine has reset the state of the CPU to a known state and loaded the first instruction into register **InstrReg**. From this point forward, the state machine changes state depending on the instructions encountered.

Fig. 4: load instruction

In the above figure, the load instruction is executed. With the help of this instruction the data is loaded from the external memory to the microprocessor. The load instruction can be immediate where the data to be loaded is the part of the

instruction .The load instruction is executed in the state machine manner where the current state starts from load 1 and end at load 6.

Fig. 5: Store Instruction

In the above figure ,the store instruction is executed. With the help of this instruction the data is loaded from the microprocessor to the external memory.

Fig. 6: branch instruction

In this execution, the data is compared with the defined value and if the condition is true, the control jumps to the defined label(address) and if the condition become false, the next instruction is executed.

Fig. 7: RTL schematic of 16 bit Microprocessor

V. CONCLUSION

Some additional features in CPU have been added like complex addition ,complex multiplication and other logical operation etc. Other Modules can be added like timer , counter ,interrupt in this which can enhance the features of the processor .Since this processor is 16 bit so it is capable of accessing 16kb of external memory. More number of input output devices can be accessed simultaneously.

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